

Nursing Sleep Promotion in Intensive Care Unit

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Abstract:

Introduction: Alterations in normal sleep patterns are common in intensive care patients and can instigate psychological and physiological dysfunctions, increasing morbidity and, consequently, mortality. **Objective:** This study will determine the impact of sleep to which sleep is impaired in intensive care patients and identify action strategies to improve sleep and comfort in these patients. **Material and Methods:** A systematic review of the literature was carried out using the PICO method. The search terms were "critically ill adult patients," "nursing care," and "sleep promotion." Nine articles were

included for analysis, published between 2018 and 2023. **Results and discussion:** Most studies confirm that patients in intensive care units have poor sleep. Evidence shows that the main causes of poor sleep in intensive care units are essentially focused on aspects inherent to the environment and the behavior of health professionals. The interventions to be implemented aim to create an environment conducive to sleep, recognizing its role in the patient's recovery. This includes stabilizing the nighttime environment, reducing staff conversations, reducing lighting and alarm call volume, and promoting relaxation techniques through massage, music therapy, mental imagery and relaxation. **Conclusions:** Sleep

promotion in this patient population should be a higher priority for nurses and intensive care professionals. Sleep should be a focus during the day and night to maintain patients' natural circadian rhythms as much as possible.

Keywords: *critically ill adult patients, nursing care, sleep promotion.*

Introduction

Sleep, rest and everything that accompanies it is now considered an active, complex and reversible phenomenon. Characterized by the absence or reduction of the response to environmental stimuli in relation to the alert state, it is a rapidly reversible state of reduced consciousness, activity and metabolism (Kirsch, 2015). The central nervous system maintains this state, influenced by stimuli from our environment, such as bright light, loud or sudden sounds, activity and temperature (Stubberud, 2015). The circadian rhythm is a universal and evolutionary mechanism that allows all animals to adapt to their environment. Exposure to changes in light and darkness is a key factor influencing this rhythm. Heart rate, body temperature, hormone secretion, and alertness change rhythmically throughout the day according to this rhythm (Hannibal and Martiny, 2013). It is a proven fact that our immune system, inflammatory responses, blood glucose regulation, gas exchange, homeostasis, and kidney function are all affected by time of day and sleep patterns. Disruption of circadian rhythms disrupts all of these regulatory systems, prolonging healing and even exacerbating disease (Chan et al., 2012).

It is common for patients in intensive care units (ICUs) to experience sleep deprivation. Of course, several factors, including the environment, ventilator, and medications, often influence sleep. Sleep deprivation is a proven cause of delirium and significantly impairs physical, immunological, and neurocognitive function (Litton et al., 2016). The sleep architecture of ICU patients is significantly altered (Auckley et al., 2018).

Despite sleeping seven to nine hours a night, ICU patients often experience frequent awakenings and lighter sleep stages. The amount

of slow wave and rapid eye movement sleep experienced by ICU patients is either excessively reduced or completely absent (Malik and Parthasarthy, 2014). ICU patients experience up to 50% total sleep during the day (Boyko and Jennum, 2013). These factors have a negative impact on recovery and can also affect sleep after recovery.

Clinical practice guidelines from the American College of Critical Care Medicine are clear: sedatives should be titrated to maintain light sedation, not deep sedation. Maintaining a light level of sedation in adult ICU patients is the best way to improve clinical outcomes, including reducing the need for mechanical ventilation and shortening ICU stay (Devlin et al., 2018).

It is crucial to understand that environmental factors such as noise and light, physiological factors such as pain, immobility, discomfort and coughing, nursing factors such as care and medication, psychological factors and most importantly, severity of illness are causes of sleep disorders.

Obviously, nurses constantly observe their patients admitted to the ICU. However, it is practically unknown to what extent they are taking care of the quality and quantity of sleep in these patients (Hopper et al., 2015). This presents ICU nurses with new challenges and responsibilities: promoting their patients' sleep.

Materials and Methods

A systematic review of the literature is one of the most effective research methods used in evidence-based practice. Its objective is to collect and summarize the results of research on a given topic in a systematic and orderly manner, thus contributing to knowledge on the subject (Mendes et al., 2008; Benefield, 2003). The

methodology used is based on the PICO (Patient, Intervention, Comparison and Outcomes) strategy. This ensures that all relevant information is included in different databases, focusing on the research question and avoiding unnecessary searches (Santos, Pimenta and Nobre, 2007).

Taking into account all the steps necessary for the use of this method, a protocol was developed to identify the studies of interest for this work, which consisted of searching search engines between May and August 2024: Ebsco and B-ONline, and the following databases: CINAHL Plus, PubMed/ MEDLINE, LILACS, Scielo, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, Cengage Learning, Academia Search Complete, Psychology and Behavioural Sciences Collection, John Wiley & Sons, Sport Discus, The Joanna Briggs Institute, U.S. National

Library of Medicine, Directory of Open Access Journals, Springer Science & Business Media and Repository of Scientific Open Access of Portugal.

A search strategy was used using the following descriptors to identify relevant studies: critically ill adult patients AND nursing care AND sleep promotion. Once all the requirements of the protocol were met, some articles that did not meet the requirements were eliminated through a methodical reductive process.

Results

The study included nine articles, which is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the Selected Studies and Main Results of the Investigations

Study(s)	Author(s)/ Year	Main results
S1: "Sleep quality and related factors in surgical patients in intensive care"	Özkan, Dine Kalaycı, 2023.	-This study used a Richards-Campbell Sleep Questionnaire (RCSQ). -Several factors affect the quality of patients' sleep, including age, type of surgery performed, pain intensity, stress score and environmental factors (ICU lights, equipment noise, room temperature, voices of other patients, and conversations of ICU staff). -The study concluded that ICU patients had poor sleep quality. -The study definitively proves that increasing the awareness of nurses and ICU staff about the factors affecting sleep quality and possible solutions by transferring the solutions to the clinic and evaluating the results, can improve the sleep quality of patients.
S2: "Factors influencing sleep quality in the intensive care unit: a descriptive pilot study in Korea"	Ahan, Hong Yil Li, Sang-Min Li a Jinwu Li; 2023.	-This study found that 19 of the 30 patients reported that the quality of sleep in the ICU was not different from that at home. The most common barriers to sleep were physical discomfort (43%), being woken up for procedures (43%) and feeling unwell (37%). Environmental factors such as noise (30%) and light (13%) were also identified as sources of sleep disturbances. -In the ICU, we can confirm that physical discomfort; interactions with the patient and the feeling of malaise are the main barriers to sleep.
S3: "Sleeping in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU): a neglected opportunity for Occupational Therapists to fill a gap in the Health Service"	Bolin A. Sweetman; 2022.	-The overwhelming majority of healthcare professionals are convinced that ICU patients have poor sleep quality, which has a negative impact on patient outcomes. -This article identifies the common factors that negatively affect sleep quality and duration and proposes evidence-based interventions to improve patients' sleep. -Factors that influence sleep include the environment, psychosocial elements, and patient care. -Affirm that health professionals can implement interventions such as guiding patients through the day, establishing sleep promotion routines, and educating patients about the use of adaptive

		equipment (earplugs, eye masks, or sound machines that play relaxing music).
S4: "Noise and Sleep Levels in Surgical ICU"	Guisasola-Rabes, Solà-Enriquez, Vélez-Pereira and Nadal; 2022.	<p>-The study was conducted over six weeks and 148 adult patients, who were not intubated or sedated, completed it. Sleep quality was assessed using the RCSQ.</p> <p>-The study found no significant association between nocturnal noise levels and sleep quality in the global sample.</p> <p>-After multivariate analysis, it was indisputably established that higher levels of nocturnal noise were correlated with lower SCHR scores. There is a clear correlation between lower levels of nighttime noise and better sleep quality in patients.</p> <p>-Patients who have difficulty sleeping at home score lower on a sleep questionnaire. If a patient has difficulty sleeping on the night of admission, they should be given hypnotic medication to help them sleep.</p>
S5: "Factors that affect sleep quality in Intensive Care Units"	Adell, Barrachina, Andrés, Graullera, Aznar, Marmaneu, Selles, Urendez; 2021.	<p>-The study definitively shows that the external factors affecting sleep quality were noise and constant exposure to light in the three periods (morning, afternoon and evening).</p> <p>-Patients admitted to the ICU show a significant deterioration in sleep quality during their stay in the ICU. The most disruptive factors were exposure to light, noise (e.g. alarms, people talking), nebulisation and certain nursing activities such as sampling or administering medicines. The age of the patients, regular alcohol consumption, the administration of benzodiazepines in the ICU, and the increase in comorbidity also had a negative impact.</p> <p>-These results clearly indicate that interventions aimed at reducing modifiable factors will help improve sleep quality in our patients.</p>
S6: "Updated Perspectives on the Management of Sleep Disorders in the Intensive Care Unit"	Nilius, Richter e Schroeder; 2021.	<p>-Research proves that treatment approaches to improve sleep in critically ill patients have focused on non-pharmacological and pharmacological strategies, with some highly promising results. However, we must recognize that pharmacological interventions alone have not provided sufficient benefit to patients.</p> <p>-ICU staff should be more aware of sleep problems and the benefits of appropriate therapies.</p> <p>-The use of existing methods and the development of new methods to prevent sleep disturbance in the ICU will undoubtedly improve the outcome of critically ill patients.</p>
S7: "Practices to promote Sleep in Intensive Care units in Brazil: a national inquiry"	Ramos, Taniguchi and Azevedo; 2020.	<p>-This study applied 118 valid questionnaires. Of these, 96 reported having a sedation and analgesia protocol, and 94 used the Richmond Agitation and Sedation Scale (RASS).</p> <p>-This research concluded that the most used measures to promote sleep were the reduction of light during the night. Earplugs to minimize noise, eye masks to reduce light, and music to induce sleep were the least used measures.</p> <p>-The study demonstrated that 99% of participants strongly believed that poor sleep quality had a detrimental impact on the patient's recovery process and that adequate sleep reduced the incidence of delirium.</p>
S8: "Pilot study: sleep in an intensive care unit promotion protocol"	Knauert, Pisani, Redecker, Murphy, Araujo, Zion a Yaggi; 2019.	<p>-This study definitively tested the effects of a sleep-promoting protocol on bedroom activity, sound, and light. This evidence that the ICU environment can be modified is an important step towards improving sleep quality in critically ill patients.</p>

		<p>-Improved sleep will undoubtedly promote circadian alignment and will also reduce delirium. The promotion protocol reduces activity and noise levels in the bedroom and improves sleep quality.</p> <p>-Providing robust sleep opportunities is an essential part of a multicomponent approach to improving ICU sleep and preventing ICU delirium.</p>
S9: "Sleep Quality and Quantity in Intensive Care Unit Patients: A Cross-Section Study"	Naik, Gupta, Soneja, Elavarasi, Sreenivas and Sinha; 2018.	<p>-This study, based on the RCSQ, defined good sleep as defined as RCSQ >50 and poor sleep as RCSQ<50. The mean RCSQ score of the patients in the study was 51.6 mm, according to the established definition.</p> <p>- We can confirm that 46.8% of the patients were having poor sleep, with a higher percentage of those who were mechanically ventilated.</p> <p>-The results clearly show that we must reduce inappropriate interventions and develop non-pharmacological techniques to allow patients to sleep comfortably.</p> <p>-It is important to note that this study had several limitations. These include the lack of measurement of noise and light levels, the dose and duration of sedatives used, and the number of procedures per patient per day. These factors could have been objectively assessed to gain a more complete understanding of the risk factors involved.</p>

Discussion

The studies on this topic are clear: sleep deprivation has a negative impact on critically ill patients admitted to intensive care. Most studies (S1, S3, S5, S6, S7, S8) confirm this and even identify the factors that trigger it. It is indisputable that the overwhelming majority of patients treated in these services are deprived of their normal sleep pattern. The evidence is irrefutable: a significant percentage of patients admitted to intensive care had poor quality sleep, a prolonged latent period and frequent awakenings. Study S5 definitively showed that critically ill patients experience frequent awakenings and approximately 50% of sleep occurs during the day. Patients consistently report poorer sleep quality, which is a source of anxiety and stress in facilities compared to sleep at home. They definitely classify this as bad sleep. These facts are well documented and widely recognized by numerous authors. It is a fact that changes in normal sleep patterns are common in patients admitted to ICUs. These changes undoubtedly lead to physiological and psychological disorders that increase morbidity and mortality. (Ugras, 2007; Friese, 2008; Nicolas et al., 2008; Yava et al., 2011).

Tamburri (2004) states that sleeping in the hospital is of lower quality than sleeping at home and sleep disorders are more distressing for the

patient. This is because there are rates of 22% of sleep deprivation for patients admitted to wards and 61% for patients admitted to units. Studies S3, S5, S7 also confirm that the majority of patients admitted to the units experience significant sleep disturbances during hospitalization. These units are hostile environments that generate physiological, social and emotional complications that, in addition to increasing mortality in critically ill patients, according to Handar et al (2015), the length of stay in these units is also harmed.

The S1 study definitively states that critically ill patients are characterized by abnormal sleep, with frequent interruptions, altered circadian rhythms, fragmented sleep, reduced REM sleep. Additionally, ICU survivors have reported that sleep deprivation and inability to sleep are among the top three sources of anxiety and stress during their stay in critically ill units. These results are in line with those of Honkus (2003), confirming that, in these contexts, patients take a long time to fall asleep and sleep is limited to stages I and II NREM. This reinforces the fact that patients admitted to units spend 40 to 50% of their total sleeping time in constant awakenings, leaving only 3 to 4% for sleep that is not perfectly restorative. These results are in line with those of Carskadon et al (2011), Besedovsky et al (2018) and Ray et al (2016).

Study S3, S5 and S7 shows that critically ill patients are exposed to various stressful situations and experiences. Patients experienced high levels of pain and discomfort, which resulted in sleep deprivation. This was the highest discomfort score during hospitalization. The results of these studies confirm the findings of Pisani et al, 2015, which state that lack of sleep or insufficient sleep causes fatigue, stress, depression and reduces the activity of the immune system, increasing the risk of infection. Lima et al (2020) also highlight that insufficient sleep leads to increased hospital stays, highlighting that it is one of the causes for the occurrence of delirium, which consequently increases mortality levels in critically ill patients.

Studies S1, S3, S5, S7, S8 and S9 clearly showed that the ICU environment is not conducive to sleep. Patients in the ICU say there is a lot of noise and bright lights. All studies have definitively shown that the main causes of sleep disorders were directly related to environmental elements such as noise, light, and clinical care interactions. The results of the studies by Engwall et al (2015), Durrington et al (2017), Fan et al (2017) and Craig et al (2018) were similar. However, in addition to these key elements, the following studies also referenced medications and acute illnesses (S6, 2018; Dres et al, 2019). In addition, health professionals, responsible for monitoring, hemodynamic stabilization and care, develop activities that inevitably impose stimuli. Of course, all these factors contribute to the patient's difficulty in maintaining adequate rest and sleep. Immunosuppression and reduced healing (Christensen, 2007) are key factors.

The main sources of noise can be verified by studying S1, S3, S5, S8 and S9. These sources include oxygen and nebulization, analytical testing, medication administration, conversations between professionals, professionals' cell phones, fan alarms, and monitors. The S4 study states that the average noise level in the ICU is 60-115 dB, which is associated with 70% of patients experiencing a higher number of awakenings and less time to sleep. Most of the awakenings caused hospitalization. Noise can cause multiple physiological damages, including cardiovascular

disorders, reduced arterial oxygen saturation, hearing loss, increased gastric secretion, and stimulation of the pituitary-adrenal. It can also lead to physiological sleep changes. Being sick and hospitalized are factors that disturb sleep/rest, and this increases even more when the person is admitted to the ICU. The World Health Organization has recommended a level of 55dB, but the constant sounds and alarms of equipment in the ICU, intubation, mobility limitations, discomfort, pain, heat or cold, lack of understanding whether it is day or night, and the perception that the family is only present for short periods (Roche et al, 2010) are caused by abrupt increases of more than 10 dB, with the decibel peak related: family visits, the physical structure (60% came from the noise of the opening of the ICU door) and 77.5% of the monitoring equipment and conversations between the various team members also meet the results of Xie et al (2009) and Auckley et al (2018).

Hetmann and Edvardsen (2020) refer to Sendelbach et al., 2015 in their article on sleep promotion in ICU units when they suggest strong recommendations for noise reduction, changing staff attitudes and educating about the results and customizing equipment alarms based on each patient's profile, daily electrode change can reduce the number of invalid alarms by 80 to 90%.

The noise of other patients was another thing that stood out, although less frequently. These facts corroborate a study conducted by Lampreia and Santos (2005), which concluded that noise is the factor that most disturbs sleep, and alarms are the main source of noise, followed by conversations among health professionals.

The World Health Organization is clear that the noise level in hospital wards should not exceed 30 dB at night to reduce sleep disturbances. Of course, some of the care provided is not necessary and routines must be adjusted to allow for nighttime sleep. These data corroborate those suggested by Olson et al (2001). It is essential to assess the client's sleep pattern, implement strategies to prevent changes in sleep pattern, create an environment that facilitates

sleep and rest, create a "quiet time" protocol, and implement measures that promote rest and sleep. These facts are in line with those presented by Ding et al, 2017 and Kandar et al, 2016.

Pre-existing sleep disturbances in S1 and S5 are a significant factor in this context. The underlying pathophysiology of the disease/injury, therapeutic interventions, and drugs should be considered. It is essential to highlight that this study reinforces the importance of the age factor. Aging increases the incidence of sleep disorders and changes in sleep architecture. This risk factor is particularly significant for ICU clinicians, as more than half of ICU admissions are attributable to patients over 65 years of age. This is a very important fact. It is essential to understand that our population is getting older. In addition, several significant obstacles to normal sleep were identified. These include the presence of pipes, wires, cables, thirst, ventilation, isolation, anxiety, and pain. These results align with those of Jun et al (2021) and Kiliç et al (2023).

S7 makes it clear that sleep disturbances and fatigue have a significant impact on physical functioning, cognitive abilities, mood, emotions, and symptoms. This can lead to delirium and other adverse effects in the ICU, which can have a negative impact on recovery. S7 revealed that 99% of participants strongly believed that poor sleep quality was detrimental to the patient's recovery process and that adequate sleep reduced the incidence of delirium. These facts are based on the studies of Mistraretti et al (2008), Figueroa-Ramos et al (2009), Trompeo et al (2011) and Kamdar et al (2015).

It is known that patients admitted to the ICU are at risk of sleep disturbances. It is clear that sleep disturbance in critically ill patients is associated with a number of serious complications, including cognitive impairment, delirium, prolonged duration of mechanical ventilation, altered immune function, and long-term psychological comorbidities. These complications may subsequently contribute to increased morbidity and mortality (Pisani et al, 2015; Pulak et al, 2016 and Devlin et al, 2018).

Undoubtedly, studies 2 and 4 demonstrate that the majority of patients did not present changes in their sleep patterns. Most authors disagree with this finding. S2 definitively found that 19 of 30 patients reported that their sleep quality in the ICU was no different from that at home. Otherwise, they definitively confirmed that the most common barriers to sleep were physical discomfort (43%), being woken up for procedures (43%), and feeling unwell (37%), as previously stated. Additionally, environmental factors such as noise (30%) and light (13%) have been identified as significant sources of sleep disturbances. S4 definitely did not find a significant association between nighttime noise levels and sleep quality in the overall sample. However, the results clearly show that there is a strong correlation between lower nighttime noise levels and better sleep quality for patients. Additionally, patients who have difficulty sleeping at home have lower scores on a sleep questionnaire. If a patient has difficulty sleeping the night they are hospitalized, they should be given hypnotic medication to help them sleep. Study S1 also found that patients operated on under elective conditions were able to sleep better than patients operated on under emergency conditions, due to acute physiological changes and comorbidities, which is more common in patients operated on under emergency conditions. This found to cause 2.46 times greater risk of adversely greater reduction in sleep quality.

The studies analyzed revealed that frequent interventions that promote sleep and comfort in critically ill patients included measures such as the reduction of light and noise during the night, the comfort of massage, the comfort of positioning and, in particular situations, the use of specific therapy indicated for this purpose. Studies S1, S3, S6, S7, S8 and S9 prove that the best way to improve the quality of sleep in critically ill patients is to reduce ambient noise and lights. Studies clearly show that minimizing sleep disruptions during the night and maintaining sleep-wake homeostasis is crucial. This can be achieved by reducing noise and unnecessary light, using non-pharmacological sleep stimulation such as earplugs, eye masks,

and relaxation techniques (silent music and massage), and promoting light during the day. These results are in line with those of Clark, 1998; Pinheiro (1998), Pimenta (2000), Almeida and Duarte, 2000 and the Order of Nurses (2010).

The S6 study also clearly describes pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches to reducing sleep disturbances. Nightingale (1989) made it clear that sleep is extremely important for the patient's recovery. He linked sleep disorders to environmental factors. S3 studies have found that eye masks and earplugs are beneficial in canceling out the effects of the Intensive Care environment, improving patients' sleep architecture (Richardson et al, 2007 and Litton et al, 2016).

We know that patients experience physical discomfort, emotional distress, and pain. In all nursing interventions, we must prioritize the promotion of their comfort. Nurses should plan interventions that allow satisfactory pain relief to be achieved through the adoption of non-pharmacological measures whenever possible. Study S1 found that 32.1% of patients in intensive care had poor sleep due to pain. S2 mentions pain as a common biological barrier to sleep. Both studies indicate a negative correlation between pain and sleep quality. Of course, there is a direct relationship between sleep and patient comfort. Nurses should therefore use the different ways to promote comfort. Rest/sleep only exists when there is some comfort. These facts are in line with what is defended by Ding et al, 2017; Owens et al, 2017; and Kandar et al, 2016.

This study definitively shows that critically ill patients in a specific hospital unit experience a change in their sleep pattern, mainly due to noise, light, and available interventions. The results of the studies analyzed make it clear that sleep in an ICU is insufficient, despite being essential for recovery. It should therefore be preserved and encouraged. It is therefore essential that members of the multidisciplinary health team work together effectively, as it is the nurse who is best placed to create a therapeutic environment, provide care and implement

interventions that allow patients to rest longer and with better quality. There are studies that refer to the protocols/bundle for sleep promotion in the ICU as an implementing intervention for sleep promotion, as it can bring together multidisciplinary professionals for education and training, adapting the protocol to the work routines of the scenarios. S7 mentions this statement as an important sleep-promoting practice in adult ICUs.

Conclusion

The diversity of problems that critically ill patients face due to physiological changes resulting from the pathological process, requires healthcare professionals to adopt a holistic approach. We must, therefore, constantly update and evolve to reduce the mortality and morbidity of these patients.

Identified as a major problem in the ICU, sleep deprivation and consequent assessment is complicated by elements of critical illness and hampered by a lack of adequate research into the reliability and validity of cost-effective assessment tools.

Taking preventive action is the best approach to managing sleep deprivation in the ICU, and management approaches should be multifaceted and include sleep routines, care plans that include sleep promotion, and appropriate medication regimens.

The literature clearly shows that there are several factors that influence the quality of sleep/rest and its division can be categorized into three ways: those inherent to the person, those inherent to professionals and those inherent to the environment of an intensive care unit. The results clearly show that the most common factors identified in the literature are: noise, glare, professional interventions and pain. Knowing these factors, the healthcare team must act to correct and minimize the main sources of discomfort through appropriate interventions.

Promoting a culture of change and mobilizing healthcare teams to institute actions that are similar to the negative consequences of not having an adequate rest pattern is essential.

Knowing how to reduce light and noise is the best way to ensure that everyone has a better quality of sleep, therefore, professionals must be made aware of the importance of sleep if we want to establish packages that guide strategies and care with an emphasis on improving sleep.

This study allowed a clear reflection on nurses' practice when dealing with critically ill patients, revealing new gaps in knowledge on the topic and opening space for the development of new research. More clinical research is urgently needed to identify effective strategies to reduce the impact of the clinical environment on patients' ability to sleep and to improve understanding of the impact of sleep deprivation and its outcomes on the patient's clinical situation. Additionally, future research should identify a method of monitoring the amount of sleep necessary and feasible to implement strategies that promote sleep, rest, and recovery while reducing complications associated with sleep deprivation.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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